

Voice of Teachers: Teaching French in Victoria, Australia

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Abstract: This research project was an attempt to address questions about the meaning that teaching French holds for French teachers. As such, it was important to give voice to those who are at the frontline of educational practices, the teachers, and in this instance, French teachers. Indeed, literature on second language (L2) acquisition in French has been slow in Victoria and elsewhere in Australia to recognise the place and role of French and of the French teacher in the language curriculum. It has gone unquestioned and largely unexamined for far too long. There is silence on the issue. Eight French teachers participated in the project and together attempted to answer the main research question: What does it mean to teach French in Victoria, Australia? The principles of van Manen's hermeneutic phenomenology were used as theory and method and pointed to a cluster of meanings around passion, creativity, resilience and growth mindset that underlined the phenomenon of teaching French among the participants. The findings also opened onto the discussion about the necessity to look at teachers' identity and more specifically that of second language teachers.

Keywords: Voice, Teacher identity, Teaching French, Hermeneutic phenomenology, Language curriculum and teaching

1. Introduction

The project presented itself as a collective of voices; those of the participants meeting the theoretical ones while also interacting with mine as a teacher-researcher. Together, these voices have captured the various themes and clusters of meanings all foundationally framed around the main research question: What does it mean to teach French in Victoria, Australia?

To better understand, one should look at the motivation and reasons underpinning a research project, and, if possible, go back to the moment when one stands in wonder at what looks like a phenomenon. This moment provides an opportunity to openly listen and let things speak and be just as they are.

It all stemmed from a question asked by a Year 7 student who wanted to understand why French is taught at schools in Australia. Indeed, there is need to ask why French is taught and survived in the second language curriculum in what some have called a highly "monolingual" society (Ang, 2011, p. 30). Srinivasan (2009, p. 47) added that the power of monolingual ideologies in Australia is evident, not only in the assumptions of white, English monolingual speakers but "also in the subjected identities of multilingual speakers who perceive themselves outside the 'imagi(nation)' of what "Australian identity and language are". The latter comment resonates deeply with me as I migrated to Australia some 20 years ago. I wonder then if I stand with the many others outside of the Australian imagi(nation) as I speak and teach an "other" language. With such considerations in mind, this research project started as a series of conversations with French teachers to understand what it means to them to teach a language that stands outside

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the imagi(nation) of Australian society. In doing so, the research revealed and exposed spaces of invisibility and the dearth of research literature on teaching French as a second language in Australia.

Presented as a language of diplomacy and trade and also as an ancestral language for 0.5% of the population in Australia (ACARA, 2021), French has been taught since 1880 following the British model of education (Baldwin, 2011). By late the 1950s and early 1960s French had almost a monopoly as the foreign language in the government sector as well as in the non-government sector of education (Mascitelli & Merlino, 2011). It is still one of the main languages taught in Victorian schools. Yet, statistics reveal that more than one out of five students have dropped language studies at the Examinations for the Victorian Education Certificate in the last ten years (Australian Curriculum and Assessment Reporting Authority (ACARA), 2023). Furthermore, according to an ACARA report and with specific reference to French, the number of students undertaking VCE French has decreased by 23.1%. It is the third greatest decrease after German and Indonesian. Questions about the importance of studying French, though not answered directly, have been the stepping board of the conversations with the participants of this project when discussing how studying French is perceived and what the associated prospects are and could be in the future.

Moreover, once the context was established: teaching French in Victoria, Australia, the project turned to the other main term in the title, “voices”. Voices of teachers are meant in this project to point to the phenomenon of teaching French in Victoria before pointing out its meaning (Merleau-Ponty, 1969). The voices of teachers offer a foray into the quiddity of the phenomenon by the description of the participants’ lived experiences within the broader perspective of hermeneutic phenomenology (Larkin et al., 2006).

In phenomenology, the notion of intentionality is central to the principle of the “voice” (Gadamer, 1979) as it indicates the inseparable link between individuals and their worlds. Therefore, expressing one’s voice presupposes that one is a conscious being who acts and interacts on purpose. One’s voice then reflects how one makes sense of one’s actions and is further linked to one’s subjectivity (Gadamer, 1977). A voice is thus personal, contextualised within the time, space and human relations, and relates to the factors that determine their *prise de parole*.

However, too often, the promotion of teachers’ and students’ voices are seen as concurrent familiar concepts in the field of educational research (Albrecht & Karabenick, 2018). Much of the research on educational aims and policies is viewed through the lens of and geared towards student achievement (Lipnevich et al., 2016). As a consequence, not enough is said about the direct implications of such on the professional lifeworld of teachers (Boadu, 2021). Even less is mentioned about how the latter view their subject and how they envisage their pedagogical reasoning in their daily practice (Alsup, 2006). As such, it was important to give voice to those who are at the frontline of educational practices, the teachers, and in this instance, French teachers. Indeed, literature on second language (L2) acquisition in French has been slow in Victoria and elsewhere in Australia to recognise the place and role of French and of the French teacher in the language curriculum. It has gone unquestioned and largely unexamined for far too long.

Furthermore, the Monash *Report on Australian Teachers’ Perception of their Work*, through an online survey of 5,497 teachers identified the challenges teachers face and explained that

72.4% of the interviewees did not envisage staying in the teaching profession until their retirement (Longmuir et al., 2022). Work conditions, administrative hassles, assessment issues, data collection requirements, an overloaded curriculum, and an unsatisfactory pay rate are described as unmanageable, unrealistic and causing burnout.

The aim of my project is then to determine that the voices of French teachers be contemplated as a phenomenon with a privileged place in the field of education in Victoria, Australia. The voice of the teachers is *le fil rouge* of this project.

2. Research Design and Methodology

By asking the question, what does it mean to teach French in Victoria, Australia?, the intent was to investigate, describe and interpret a phenomenon which proved to be unique and complex. From an ontological point of view, this meant that the research project had to describe and abstract the attributes and perceptions, properties, features, and characteristics of teaching French from the existential data collected. From an epistemological point of view, the main objective was to reconstruct meaning from the lived experience of the participants by evidencing the evidence about teaching French and by deepening the evidence through hermeneutic interpretation (Henriksson, 2012) of what it means to teach French.

van Manen's approach (2023) was specifically chosen and it articulates methodological principles that resonate throughout the project in its attempt to understand the world, cultivate a disposition of sensitivity and openness, and uncover experiences of meanings and meanings of experiences. It has also led to the expression of the exemplary aspect of the phenomenon depicted in the rich textual descriptions of the said experience (van Manen, 2006). Furthermore, the contextualisation of the phenomenon is linked to the subjectivity of the participants who achieve the actualisation of their lived experience in context with others at their school and as part of the wider community of French teachers. van Manen's (2017) hermeneutic phenomenology allows me also to express my beliefs and capture the intersubjective lifeworld from which the phenomenon emanates (Finlay, 2003) as I form part of the community of French teachers too.

This explains that the meaning of the phenomenon was constructed in a dialogical movement within our experience: both that of the participants and mine. The theoretical framework thus needed to consider my contradictions as a teacher-researcher called on the one side to be removed scientifically from the experience and on the other to be open to interactions with the participants while weighing constantly these contradictions. It has, enabled both the experience of the participants and mine as possible intersubjective expressions of the phenomenon of teaching French (van Manen, 2016). In addition, using van Manen's hermeneutic phenomenology proved essential to support my research project in its intent to also stand in the field of research on education in a pedagogical way (van Manen, 2016).

2.1 Participants and Voices

The principal step to answer phenomenological concerns and questions is to find the research participants to lend their voices to the project. I first asked the Head of French at the school where I was working, and she offered to contact a member of the French staff on another campus of the school. The latter agreed to take part in the project. From then, the other participants were selected through a snowballing method (Parker et al., 2019). Once teachers

had completed the interview, they took the initiative of inviting a colleague of theirs to be part of the project.

Snowballing is neutral as researchers are not influenced by personal bias in the process. Nevertheless, one could argue that the gatekeepers, those through whom entry to the project is gained, could exercise a form of control on the research project because they were the ones who selected the participant (Groenewald, 2004). This issue was resolved by ensuring that the participants did not come from the same school the participants worked at, nor from the same sector of education in Victoria.

Eventually eight participants were chosen. It was thought that the more detailed and comprehensive the data collected is, the fewer the number of participants necessary (Hennink & Kaiser, 2022). This cautionary measure thus allowed to focus on an in-depth description and interpretation of the rich data collected during the 60-minute interviews and via other forms of communication, such as emails, phone calls and in-person meetings.

As our conversations progressed, two teachers changed schools, one stopped teaching to become a casual relief teacher, another left to teach in another state, another left their school to teach in a community school, one retired and one left the school environment to teach exclusively in an online campus.

The following table gives a snapshot of the group of eight teachers: who they are, with the gender they identify with, their ethnic and social background, their professional experience in and outside of teaching, the type of school they worked in at the moment of the research, the number of years they had taught and if they taught only French or another subject. The eight teachers selected represented a range of experience. They were at different stages of their teaching careers; some were a few years into their career while others had numerous years of teaching. Some had always been teachers while others came to teaching after a career in another field. All interviewees, it is to be noted, willingly offered to answer the questions and participate in the project.

Table 1: Participants' Data

Name	Gender identity	Social background	Number of years of teaching experience	Types of schools worked at	Experience outside of teaching	Other subjects
1-Adele	F	Australian	5	C & I	N	Science
2-Darren	M	Australian	30	Intl, I, C & Govt	Y	English & Humanities
3- Greg	M	French	15	Intl & C	N	Humanities
4-Carrie	F	Mauritian	10	Intl & I	N	ESL
5-Anne	F	Australian	40	Intl, C & I	N	-
6-Nadia	F	French	12	C& Govt	N	-
7-Ron	M	Australian	20	I & Govt	N	Latin
8-Tanya	F	Australian	22	Intl, I, C & Govt	Y	German

Note: This table shows data about participants as explained above. Abbreviations used are (Intl) for international schools, (C) for Catholic schools, (I) for independent schools and (Govt) for government Schools.

2.2 The Interviews

The participants and I decided on the time practicalities of the interviews to be conducted. We deemed that a 50–60-minute interview was reasonable rather than breaking it into a series of shorter interviews. To a certain extent, this mimicked teaching times at school.

The phenomenological interview is usually a one-to-one interview and is the principal method by which a phenomenological researcher gathers the lived experiences of the participants (Adams & van Manen, 2017; Kvale, 1996). The method of interviewing the participants was more of a conversational nature. The interviews started by discussing details about the participants' consent forms and were presented as a conversation in which we would engage. Following van Manen's method (2016) of hermeneutic interviewing or conversational interviews, I did not engage in an open-ended interview but rather undertook semi-structured interviews guided by the subsidiary questions. Even if the questions were pro forma, they were often reworded or even occurred at different times in the interviews according to the conversations engaged with the participants (Lauterbach, 2018).

Sets of answers were collected from the interview and the ensuing phone calls were recorded and dated as they gathered the lived experiences of the participants at different moments. Many participants preferred to do a phone call after the first interview rather than emailing, explaining that it was easier for them to talk about their experience rather than write about it. They also thought that it would take them longer to phrase their reflections about the questions being asked and that it would lose the pre-reflective nature of our conversations, or as Adele called it, the "spontaneity of our bavardage" (the French word *bavardage* is translated as "chats"). We then agreed that interviews or phone calls gave us an immediate expression of what the phenomenon we were trying to understand looks like.

In my notes, I also wrote as a reminder to myself after the first interviews that it was sometimes better not to ask too many questions. Moments of silence captured on Zoom were sometimes rich sources of data too that have also been explored and interpreted. Furthermore, I encouraged a rapport based on a sense of shared identity and notified participating teachers that all answers and reactions were valid and would form part of the final transcript. The lived experiences came in the forms of anecdotes, memories and reflections. Both the participants and I engaged in deep conversations emanating from the questions being asked or from replies that triggered further prompts. The final transcripts were reviewed and vetted by the participants.

The teachers interviewed were undeniably enthusiastic about their participation in the project. They even commented afterwards that they had appreciated being invited to share their experiences as French teachers. Adele wrote in her email after having read the transcript, "I actually had goosebumps reading the transcript. I think it was a really powerful conversation that we had". After reading their transcript, participants sometimes chose to express their ideas in other words, to correct, edit or reinforce what they had said. Transcripts of the different versions have been kept and helped examine the differences both in the expression of the ideas and in the idea itself.

2.2.1 The Interview Protocol

To ensure ethical research protocol, I used consent agreement forms. Before each interview, I emailed the consent form to each participant and at the beginning of each interview, I explained the following points:

- that this is a research project done within the requirements of a PhD project at Monash University
- that the research had obtained approval from the Monash University Human Research Ethics Committee (MUHREC) in 2018
- the voluntary nature of participation in the research project
- the purpose of the research is to represent the phenomenon of teaching French through the voices of teachers
- the protocols of data gathering through snowballing
- the interview protocols like the length of the interview
- the procedures to protect confidentiality

Before, during, and even after the interview, I discussed risks about the disclosure of information. Even though I used a standard consent form, I explained to the participants that I would be the only one to view the consent form and thus to know the identity of those who had signed it. Confidentiality, as explained above, was central to the proceedings and helped reduce tension between the participants and me and promoted sincere responses on their part. Apart from confirming to the participants that neither their name nor the name of their school would be disclosed, I also informed them that all Zoom video recordings would be deleted once the research project was completed, leaving only the transcripts as research documents.

Despite the stability of the verification procedures to represent the phenomenon under study, there could be grounds to contest phenomenology's lack of scientific objectivity regarding credibility, transferability, dependability and conformability (Guba & Lincoln, 1999). That is why since the inception of this project, I was faced with the necessity to define the status of the object of the research and the theoretical framework provided by hermeneutic phenomenology as understood by van Manen (2023).

2.3 The Ethics of Bracketing and Reflexivity: The Researcher's Positionality

If the boundary between the researcher and the participants is deemed necessary in maintaining objectivity and ensuring validity, it has by now, however, been well argued that the elimination of subjectivity in qualitative research is impossible (Davies & Dodd, 2002; Errasti-Ibarrondo et al., 2018). It is thus accepted that in phenomenological research the researcher also becomes an actor sharing in the lived experience of the participant. Indeed, my emic position as a French teacher did not allow me any form of distance from what was being said. I thus felt part of the phenomenon and allowed myself to be moved by it.

Bracketing combined with reflexivity (Chan et al., 2013) was then the methodological device to ensure rigour in my interpretation of the phenomenon. It started from the moment I stood in wonder before the lifeworld experience of teaching French and continued throughout the research process. Bracketing as a reflexive method based on van Manen's tenets (2017) has indeed provided me with an awareness of my positioning as a teacher-researcher. I had to gauge potential biases that could have mitigated my interpretation of participants' views, the nature of the methodology and the nature of the phenomenon where each participant brings their individual story (Barnacle, 2004). Consequently, an implicit part of the ethical practice involved acknowledging and locating my position as a researcher within the research process (Holmes, 2020) and identifying my personal and professional assumptions as a researcher.

It is understood that the quest for reliability and validity depends on identifying and recognising the relationship between the subject(s) and the intentional object (Munhall, 1989). In the present research, the subject is both the participants and the researcher-teacher I am, while the object is the intentional object of teaching French. The interaction openly identified and recognised as such between the subject and the object of the analysis thus did not compromise the validity of the findings (Fuster Guillen, 2019).

The participants' experiences and my experiences are both recognised, valued, and described (Davies & Dodd, 2002). I understood the lifeworld of the participants through the foregrounding and appropriation of my being in the world as a teacher (Gadamer, 1979 and Regan, 2012). I also maintain that my emic positionality did not affect my understanding of the participants' experiences and allowed instead for a natural flow of conversation during the interview. I remained vigilant and conscious of the power dynamics due to the nature of my emic position and the ensuing possibility of exerting influence over the participants because of our professional relationship.

My research was thus based on a transparent sharing of professional identities with my research participants: we are all French teachers in secondary schools in Victoria. Bracketing both as a method and an ethical process was thus essential and valuable to elaborate the relationship between the participants and me.

2.4 Memos

Memoing (Groenewald, 2004) is another critical data source in qualitative research that I have used in this study. My memos can be listed as follows:

- observational notes during the interviews
- theoretical notes when I reflected on the experience of the phenomenon
- methodological notes; my reflection on bracketing my presuppositions during the conversation with the teachers
- my answers to the emails received from the teachers commenting on the transcript of the interview sent to them
- the notes from the phone calls and the in-person meetings

2.5 The Research Questions

The research questions emphasise the study of the phenomenon and attempt to prompt interpretation of the meaning the participants bring to the phenomenon of teaching French. Furthermore, they are infused with a need to clarify and understand essential dimensions of knowledge (Moustakas, 1994) about the phenomenon of teaching French in Victoria and offer a solid foundation for the project. They have been phrased to explore and understand the lived experience of the participants, the meaning of their experience, and to listen to their stories (Nixon, 2017). They assume two forms: a main research question and associated sub-questions. The main question is broadly a statement about the issue being examined within the context of the research design (Creswell & Creswell, 2017). However, with any research questions, while the reply is relative to the questions asked, the meaning can exceed what is being asked.

- *Main research question*
What does it mean to teach French?
- *Sub-questions:*
What motivates French teachers to teach French?

How French is perceived in the curriculum?

What it means to French online?

What it means to teach French in the future?

2.6 Data Analysis

This section opens with the complex process of creating a verbatim, identifying descriptive statements and finally moving to data analysis. The first step after the interviews was to work on the transcription and the video images of the Zoom interviews. Sonix.AI software was used to transcribe the conversations and to respect the participants' word-for-word intervention. The transcription produced authenticity as the paraverbal cues, such as the silences, hesitations, repetitions and stammering, were maintained.

2.6.1 The Descriptive and Interpretive Statements

Once the transcriptions were collected, thorough and meticulous work was necessary to detect and represent the structure of the experience in the verbatim. I numbered the pre-determined questions and the answers to facilitate the subsequent phases of refinement of the verbatim and sequential reorganisation of the descriptions. Moreover, throughout the analysis, which is also a process of abstraction, the numbering of questions and answers made it possible to retrieve and follow through each participant's experience (Finlay, 2014). Structural statements or minimal units of meaning were then named and clustered into descriptive categories from which meaning was later abstracted.

Pattern finding, cluster making, and categorising (Sundler et al., 2019), with NVivo at first and manually most of the time, gave a sense of organisation (Finlay, 2011). I was conscious that when using these data analysis methods, it took time for meaning to be uncovered. This process, however, supported the main principles of phenomenology that demands that the meaning of the lived experience emerges through iterative readings of the descriptive statements about the phenomenon in its temporal, spatial and relational modalities (van Manen, 2017). This process, thereby, ensured rigour and credibility via the phenomenological research method undertaken.

Figure 1: My Steps in Data Interpretation

2.6.2 The Units of Meaning

After working on the data, the explication process consisted of summarising each interview, validating it, using field notes and memos to delineate descriptive statements, and clustering

units of meaning to find interrelationships. To achieve the project's aim, varied examples were selected with thoughtfulness and reflection because powerful phenomenological descriptions are composed of examples that reveal the profound significance or meaning structures of the lived experience (Hycner, 1985). In short, the phenomenological description and interpretation of the phenomenon is a combination of the examples identified and cited.

Eventually, the analysis of such statements was inceptual and not merely semantic, interpretive or conceptual. It revealed unique insights into the phenomenon (van Manen, 2017). Figure 1 captures the steps in data collection and interpretation.

3. Findings: What the Data Says

The findings illustrated how the is-ness of the phenomenon appears and takes shape as part of its being-in the world (Heidegger, 1962). Each subsidiary question became in turn the focal point of analysis to answer the main research question. The figure below summarises the key points established. It brings together the research question and its sub-questions with the main research question as the focal point. The information has been placed in the Figure 2 to underline that all findings are connected and all form part of a whole clustered around the main research question.

Figure 2: The Synthesised Findings

The first sub-question was: What motivates teachers to teach French? The answer to the question took the form of personal stories about how some participants were first attracted to the language before entering the profession of teaching French. Others elaborated on intrinsic forms of motivation despite pressure and doubt experienced as part of their teaching. In contrast, others evoked demotivation and, in one instance, a feeling of amotivation that led to retirement from the profession. Therefore, the research offered a description of the lived experience of what motivates French teachers in their quotidian practice. The teachers' comments uncovered a complex pattern and various forms of motivation prompted by strong emotions expressed or inferred also in the moments of silence during our conversations. The

findings to that question then presented “passion” (Armstrong, 2013) as an overarching notion that sustains motivation while transcending it simultaneously. It was, however, made clear that once the passion was lost, the motivation to teach French was lost too.

I asked the subsidiary question, what motivates teachers to teach French, at different times during the interview. For some, it appeared at the very start, and I phrased it as a question about the calling to teach French in general. For others, it came as an extension from or was woven into the question about the satisfaction of teaching French. The question also appeared when teachers described their daily experience in class, but it was present all through the flow of our conversation.

Whether the question was asked or implied, all participants discussed their beliefs and reasons for their choice of career, their personal and professional attributes as French teachers, values that hone their role as French teachers and the experiential background they brought to their teaching. The following mind map (Figure 3) explicates how the different points identified and presented in the sub-sections create a connection with the research question. The blocks are assembled to draw attention to parallels, comparisons and contrast identified in the participants’ comments about forces of motivation and factors causing demotivation to teach French. At no time during the chapter are these forces and factors seen as antithetical to each other; they allow, on the contrary, for a complex image to emerge about the experience of teaching French.

Figure 3: Motivations for Teaching French

Adele explained that:

For me, it is passing on my own passion for learning the language, given that I'm a native English speaker, I had to go through the journey of learning a second language myself. And I thoroughly enjoyed it, both at school and at university and then living over in France.

Anne expressed how the school context influenced explained her moments of demotivation: Being a teacher is one of the most challenging jobs. This needs time and regular contact. Lots of contact hours. French cannot be “present” in a school which does not respect and value second language learning as much as other “important” subjects.

For his part, Darren linked his amotivation to assessments:

Assessment can be an overkill. And this is an old fashioned old, old fuddy-duddy, I suppose, when I found that the ongoing assessment just became the be-all and end-all. It just freaked the girls out. I've never seen so much anxiety...the whole school is driven by this anxiety, which was unnecessary because I was finding ways of trying to get out of this situation.

Eventually, Darren lost his motivation to continue working in a school whose value system clashed with his own, even if as he argues during his "*chant du cygne*", he tried to rise above his work conditions and find means to help his students until the very end of his teaching. He knew, however, that he had reached the end of his career as a French teacher when he lost all "passion" to continue. Darren is now officially retired.

The second subsidiary question was: How is French perceived within the school curriculum? The question branched out into avenues of questioning and exploration of perceptions of French as a subject taught within the school curriculum and how the French teacher is perceived. The perceptions uncovered are not atomistic in meaning, but rather when associated together form a whole, from which the meaning of what is perceived appears. They are multifaceted as the perceived, French, as a subject, is perceived by the French teacher (the participant) but also by others within their particular school situation, like the other teachers, the students learning French, the administration and the school community at large. As the clusters of meanings unfold, the perceiver (the teacher) also becomes the perceived, such as when the participants reveal how they are perceived in their role as French teachers at their school. Together and through an "intertwining", an intersubjective exploration the perceived and the perceiver exist (Merleau-Ponty, 2012) and form the presence of French in the school. Darren commented that:

It appeals to the students, you know, many, many come to French and they say, oh, I want to study French, and I want to know about France. And I want to know about the culture. There's something about the culture that appeals to the students. It's very France-centered.

Figure 4: Perceptions of French Subject and Teaching Experience

Overall, Figure 4 points to the uniqueness of the participants' perceptions and at times even points to the contrasting views they hold. Nadia explained her unique teaching position:

I want to show French culture and French Arab culture, mainly from North Africa. I have a contemporary approach to teaching culture as I think it is important to talk about immigration in its positive and negative aspects and racism in French society. I want my students to understand that today in France couscous is the most popular French dish. It can be seen as a personal view but in my view, it is important not to confine France and French culture to mere stereotypes.

Overall, participants linked the perception of the French teacher to that of the subject they taught where both were interlinked. They explained that they would wear French paraphernalia like scarves or French shirts for special events at their schools as these added to their identity as a French teacher.

The preliminary finding probed also into the idea of cultural capital (Bourdieu, 1990), long associated with the perception of French as part of the language curriculum but which moved onto shifting grounds while wondering if such capital would persist. Darren explained:

I always felt the French should hold a rock-solid presence. However, you can't always control what is going on in the world. It is too quick for one to gauge where we are going. 50 years ago, in Australia, the two leading foreign languages taught in schools were French and German. Moreover, now you've got a multiplicity of languages being taught, all of relevance to the students choosing the languages but not French.

The next question stemmed from the above considerations about what teaching French could mean in the future. As we slowly wound down the natural course of our conversations, the participants talked about the future of language education in Australia and more specifically about the prospects of teaching French as part of the language curriculum in Victoria. We talked about the place, or rather the perception, that French holds in the curriculum; the system in which it is taught; the culture of the school and the culture of assessment associated with the wider school culture; the motivation to teach French; and the place of the teacher as an agent of their teaching. Interestingly, as we thought and discussed the future and the idea of novelty, we were often taken back to a network of ideas and concepts we had touched upon before as if the future, present and past were inextricably connected.

Much could be added about the much needed and hoped-for process of change and the learning environment required for the implementation of a more authentic pedagogy discussed by the participants. Or, still, one could discuss further the need to revisit the school curriculum to raise the profile of languages in the curriculum while providing support in various forms to ensure capacity building and professional development among French teachers. Another point dominated the discussion: the need to foster a collaborative culture among French teachers, the Federation of French Teachers, the school in which they teach and the external parties, like other language federations and university researchers. The DET is often mentioned for the role it needs to play to protect and enhance language diversity in the curriculum (Scrimgeour, 2022). This all-inclusive environment leaves the teacher as the main agent of change, capable through creativity and self-reflection of shifting towards innovative pedagogies to meet students' needs within a supportive school environment (Priestley & Drew, 2019). Carrie emphasised in her last comment that:

It is psychologically, emotionally, intellectually, scientifically proven that learning a second language helps in all fields of life. So, it is important to educate French teachers now and in the future about such beneficial aspects of our teaching. Maybe it's time to start all over again and rethink the training L2 teachers need in our contemporary world.

Teachers, hence, must develop effective strategies to ensure coherence and continuity of French programs in primary through to secondary schools and further on to university.

Anne explained that:

Because I recognised the need to adapt constantly, always essential in teaching! but the love of French and teaching flickered and has not been extinguished!

The future of teaching French is depicted as flowing from its present and past while questioning both. The findings ended with advice that current teachers could give future French teachers. Conversations pointed to creativity (Collard & Looney, 2014) as a responsive teaching strategy, the need to review assessment forms and policies both online and during F2F classes, the role of French in the language curriculum and, more widely, the school curriculum. Most of all, there was a desire for French to be viewed as a current and positive language that could speak to the realities of students, not as a foreign language relegated to the textbook and the four walls of the classroom. Thus, it was hoped that the students would develop an interest in the language and the motivation to speak and learn it in return.

They forcefully underlined that to thrive in these critical times, French teachers need a pedagogy with a desire for challenge and an ability to cope with difficulty. In the past, it may have seemed sufficient to know how to teach, to have content knowledge and language skills and apply them going forward in one's teaching practice. However, as the nature of teaching is constantly evolving with routine tasks, like corrections and report-writing being taken care of by ever-more sophisticated algorithms, teachers need to develop a thirst for knowledge. More than ever before does teaching French require French teachers to be leaders in as much as they seek out hard-to-acquire expertise that can help them succeed in their new teaching environment.

3.1 Summary

As part of their teaching qualities, participants have shown cognitive skills and emotional intelligence to gauge the school system they work in and sometimes against (Golombek & Doran, 2014). They have also demonstrated the capacity to align their teaching with a changing and challenging environment. Indeed, they appreciate that challenges can also come with solutions and that they are ready to amend, modify, and re-evaluate their teaching conditions, given the support to do so (Ang, 2011; Benson, 2016). In other words, the participants have argued that French teachers can be leaders with a positive mindset, a creative mind and a willingness to continue learning (Komorowska, 2013). They also demonstrate acute attention to what the school, the larger context of the community and society have to say about their profession (Priestley & Drew, 2019).

Furthermore, their pedagogy was not merely to reproduce pre-determined methodologies but were spontaneous and responsive ways to speak back to the proliferation and intensification of the duties assigned to teachers and face their teaching environment's challenges while addressing their students' needs (Chisholm et al., 2019). Their creative planning and teaching practice were open to their teaching beliefs and the needs of their students. Teaching French, for them, did not just happen; it was more of a consciously responsible, well-established

practice (Galvin & Todres, 2012) and a critically intentional act that responded to the situational requirements of their classrooms.

They were autonomous intrinsically motivated agents of their teaching (Bandura, 1997). They knew of the importance of reaching a high level of competence, experience and expertise and argued that the same perseverance was required of future teachers to keep French in the curriculum for the “beauty of the language” and its “cultural *savoir*”.

Consequently, when the participants jazzed their French teaching practice, they showed how they taught with leadership for a purpose and vision. Indeed, during all our conversations and despite the many challenges of teaching French, the participants talked about the joys, satisfaction, and “fun” they enjoy and pass on to their students, including the “aha moments”. Through their voices, the participants have uncovered the heart, the mind, and the act of what it means to teach French.

4. Discussion

This study demonstrates that leadership is at the heart of teaching French. French teachers see themselves as leaders capable of decision-making and decision-taking in the interest of their students, mindful of their students’ needs and with a vision and strategy (Godfrey & Olson, 2019) for the continued presence of French in the school curriculum. The reconstruction of the phenomenon presented an intricate web of interconnections among the vibrant concrete experiences of the participants, uncovering their voices during all the changes, challenges and joys they faced in teaching French.

Figure 5: Teaching and Leading

The participants described what they do and feel, the struggles they meet, the resistance they offer, and the values they believe in and that they share with others. They revealed a dynamic identity in that they exercised their agency with intentionality and purpose, being neither complacent nor neutral actors while teaching French. That is why I position teaching with leadership (Figure 5) as the primary meaning derived from the main research question, what it means to teach French. In other words, in their teaching practice, the participants proved that, by definition, a French teacher is called to be a leader. The term “leadership” is here preferred

to agency (Bucchanan, 2015; Chisholm et al., 2019) or self-efficacy (Bandura, 1997) because it is directly linked to participants' comments in that they envisaged themselves as "leaders" of their classroom and "leading" their students.

4.1 The French Teacher as a Teacher-Leader

Reappropriating the word "leadership" with a Bakhtinian turn, I refer specifically here to teacher leadership as the defining, asserting and powerful agentic voice of the French teacher. Bakhtin explains that a word or term exists in other people's intentions, "it is from there that one must take the word and make it one's own" (Bakhtin, 2010). Leadership as a term exists in education and other fields but I use it in the following specific way for this study.

First, to explain the notion of teaching French with leadership, one needs to turn to the etymology (Oxford Learners' Dictionaries, 2025) of the verb "to lead" as the act of exercising leadership. In its Latin translation, to lead is *intro ducere*. In other words, when one guides, one guides into something new or different. This is the definition that is here retained and applied to teaching French. Hence, teaching French entails more than imparting content knowledge.

Teaching takes place in a social context within the classroom situation and beyond. The French classroom becomes a site of transformative practices of social interactions where learners develop a social persona other than their own as they encounter a language and culture that is neither that of their first culture and language nor that of the target language and culture altogether. While acquiring and imparting language skills, teaching French creates a site of a highly dialogical imagination in the interstices of a third space (Bhabha & Rutherford, 2006). Second, teaching French is even more complex and dynamic in that it is further characterised by transnational flows of ideas (Kramsch, 2013) and people teaching the subject. Many French teachers met during the research project, including some of the participants, are from overseas and teach French in Australia. Some are from Africa, the Middle East, Canada, France, Europe, and the other parts of the *Francophone*, French-speaking world. All embrace French as their first or second language and all have brought to "their" French an identity of its own, a "je ne sais quoi" as Nadia explained: "I bring my perspective to the teaching of French. Because I am French, but I am French of Moroccan origin, therefore I am '*une maghrébine*' teaching French".

In other words, teaching French leads the teacher to become, over and above the requirements of their profession, brokers and mediators of words and images depicting the target language and culture in and against a monolingual Australia (Clyne, 2008). They thus pass on, carry over, and transmit words, images, and imaginaries from one culture to another, from one space to another.

Third, through the twists and turns of the data collected and interpreted within the parameters of hermeneutic phenomenology, the findings point out the necessity to lead with passion while teaching French despite sometimes the perception the teachers develop about themselves and their subject, to express leadership as a creative responsive strategy used within new sites of teaching, such as teaching online and to think creatively about the prospects of teaching French in years ahead. In a nutshell, leadership is exercised in the quotidian practice of teaching French.

Eventually, all participants defined themselves as leaders of their teaching, demonstrating pedagogical and dispositional commitment and the energy to inspire and challenge their

students within and despite sometimes the constraints of the school setting (Danielson, 2007). In their role as leaders, the French teacher endeavours to guide and most importantly inspire their students to be learners ready to embrace the challenges of learning a second language even when doing so might prove difficult.

A question arises about the whole concept of teaching with leadership as an impractical wish or a vision with no definite purpose. However, it could also be an idea whose time has come because today, and more than ever before, leaders have to figure out effective actions in their context and persuade themselves and others that they can do it (Sanborn, 2008). The next subsections attempt to answer these queries by recalling what the participants said about teaching with leadership in their quotidian practice. The comments from the participants in the Figure 6 serve as a signpost to the next section.

Figure 6: Participants' Comments about Leadership

4.1.1 Leading why: To Keep a Purpose and a Vision

The metaphor used by Carrie, one of the participants, “keeping one’s eyes open”, unveils a pedagogical attitude that can change the system when French teachers step back from institutional directives to assess how to teach French and respond actively and intentionally to their students’ needs. By creating such a vision for their teaching, French teachers can adjust, modify, and craft the required strategies to sustain their teaching goals. They are not left to swing and sway to the winds of the changes and pressures engendered by the system and the policies. Instead, they can assess their teaching practice and recognise their successes while paying acute attention to areas of their teaching that need improvement.

Teaching French with a vision becomes an essential pedagogical tool in the classroom and transforms the latter into a space where the teacher teaches purposefully and with leadership. As such, the teachers’ vision empowers them and gives them a voice against systemic instructions and top-to-bottom mandates that often leave them with limited decisional and instructional powers (Hefferman et al., 2021).

Consequently, it could be argued that teaching French with “eyes open” conveys to the French teacher a vision that can reveal their beliefs as educators, how they conceive their subject, what motivates them to continue teaching, the strategies aligned with evidence-based research they put in place in times of change, and how their visioning becomes a viable tool to empower them today and forge a future for their subject despite the threats foreseen. Thus, French teachers, according to the participants, guide their work mindfully today and shape tomorrow’s

teaching prospects while redefining their role as “leaders” (Dugan et al., 2017) in their classrooms.

It must be recognised that there is a downside to the definition or re-definition of teaching French as an intentional act of leadership. While the participants may be tacitly acknowledging that French teachers are leaders of their classroom practices, they also have admitted that their authority outside such a paradigm is too often short-changed, thus perpetuating the idea and the perception of “I am just a French teacher”, and the ensuing idea of subordination: “I’ve never climbed the ladder”. In these times of disruption, the notions of leadership discussed may reflect only a self-defeating purpose (Fisher et al., 2016) and vision with no practicality in a school context. However, such times may also open a space for significant change to occur.

To end this section and in answer to the previous question, the words of Dewey cited by Archambault (1964) will be made to resound with those of the participants in reaffirming what it is to teach with leadership. In this instance, teachers need to keep their eyes open as they are not “expected merely to obey, or be like a cog in a wheel, expected merely to respond to and transmit external energy” (Archambault, 1964, p. 205).

4.1.2 Leading how: With a Growth Mindset and by Being Mindful

The question then is to know how to lead when one teaches French with a “growth mindset” (Dweck, 2006) and becomes a mindful leader. This also opens a discussion on how one leads for a purpose and vision when teaching French and what teaching French looks like when the French teacher becomes a mindful leader harnessing engagement and commitment to lead in their teaching practice. None of the participants, however, used the term “growth mindset”, but they all alluded to it on their particular terms and in their own words.

In other words, I use the idea specifically to explain how to lead with a growth mindset, highlighting the importance of growing one’s mind and skills during one’s career (Zhang & Zhang, 2021) to teach French effectively. Indeed, the effect of a growth mindset is to transform the meaning of challenges so that they are seen as opportunities to grow one’s teaching skills rather. The participants showed that they believed in their ability to surmount the challenges of teaching French be it online or in F2F settings. There were moments of doubt, feelings of failure but not a sense of setback.

The findings connected the participants’ sense of motivation and evolving emotional regulation strategies (Albrecht & Karabenick, 2018) with their passion for teaching French. and illustrated how their adaptive teaching strategies (Freeman & Richards, 1993) helped them pursue their teaching goals to meet both their students’ needs, despite expected and unexpected challenges like teaching online exclusively for nearly two years. All recognised the importance of growing and adapting pedagogical skills for teaching (Toure, 2008; Collard & Looney, 2014) in general and teaching French in particular in a fast-paced, changing learning and teaching environment. Endowed with such a mindset, participants explained how the challenges changed in meaning and intensity and how they saw the challenges as opportunities to grow their students’ abilities and their own.

There is therefore an urgent need to address the issue of a growth mindset in teaching and among teachers, especially in an age of disorienting changes (Toure, 2008), and how teachers shape their thinking, motivation, and teaching ability for this purpose. The sparse literature on teacher growth mindset constitutes a critical knowledge gap. Consequently, it is important to

show that by listening to teachers' voices, one can better gauge their need to grow their skills and mindset in leading their classroom activities and facing the daily challenges of teaching. The participants knew and understood furthermore that the purpose of teaching is multifield (Barkhuizen, 2017) and that teaching and learning are not only cognitive practices but also emotional ones, with both aspects combining to make the students' experience a rich, positive and stimulating one. Too often the changes impelled by the new mantras in education about teacher performativity are guided solely by increased attention to constructivist approaches to learning and problem-solving skills and overlook that teaching and learning are emotional practices (Konidari & Samara, 2021). Somehow cognitive-driven reforms do not capture all of what is teaching and does not go to the heart of the practice (Hargreaves, 2001). As Ron, one of the participants said, teaching has the colour of emotions. Teaching expresses emotions that can stimulate learning or bore the students. The term "mindful" here captures notions of the emotional practice (Hargreaves, 2001), of a tactful pedagogy (van Manen, 2016) by appealing to emotional intelligence (Goleman, 2024).

Participants remained thus mindfully centred on their French students' unique needs and to guide and lead they needed to create favourable conditions for their students despite the numerous demands of an administrative system too often lacking in vision and purpose (Taxer & Gross, 2018). They recognised that they become, through practice, more attentive to the needs and emotions of their students (Hargreaves, 2001). They argue, however, that such a vision demands constant energy, enthusiasm, and positive, optimistic attitudes for them to be effective in their teaching and to encourage their students to develop their potential. They lead with emotion and passion.

These constant demands generate, however, anxiety and stress (Murphy & Mannix-McNamara, 2021). All the participants indeed mentioned how their wellbeing is affected by the constant challenges they face in their profession. They explained how they were successful at times in negotiating the delicate balance between the many roles they play. They deplored, nevertheless, that, at other times, they failed to do so and faced deeply challenging moments. Hence, they have learnt to know themselves, to recognise their feelings and their belief systems to continue leading their class. Even if they showed resilience and adapted their teaching to suit the demands of the moment with creative pedagogies (Henriksen & Cain, 2020) away from the *sentiers battus*, the well-trodden paths, they acknowledged the considerable difficulty they faced.

The Monash University report while investigating the root causes of teacher shortage in schools, confirmed the need to give due consideration to teacher wellbeing (Hefferman et al., 2021), which has been the subject of much research lately (Murphy & Mannix-McNamara, 2021). In positive psychology, Seligman (2018), among others expounds that wellbeing is a concept linked to the positive emotion of happiness and satisfaction, which leads to job satisfaction. Optimal wellbeing is then a state where one can reach one's goal while coping with the other stresses of life situations (McLean & Smith, 2025).

4.1.3 Leading when: in Times of Disruption

In March 2020, we faced a watershed moment for education online during the Covid-19 pandemic. Teaching as a leader took on its full meaning as the four walls of the teaching classroom fell apart and left the teacher with no other teaching plan than to teach with initiative in replacement of what was the norm. The approaches for instruction originally conceptualised

for in-person four-walled classroom setups had to be rethought and re-created to suit remote learning with not much input from administration and other stakeholders (Gacs et al., 2020). The teacher was suddenly at the core of teaching and was viewed as such; public perception of teachers changed drastically during this time (Hefferman et al., 2021).

There had never been a time like that before; no training or teacher education had prepared teachers for that moment in time. Yet, teachers were instructed to continue teaching and fostering learning without being given time or means to consider best teaching practices. It resulted in complicated situations of synchronous and asynchronous lessons and even, in some cases, ineffective practices that threatened teaching and teachers' self-efficacy. Teachers then demonstrated leadership in having to constantly appraise their teaching pedagogical needs daily in a time of sheer inequality where some had the means to teach online and others did not (Nanda & Ryan, 2023). They had to create a site to teach where co-existed needs of "gentleness and firmness moving towards the subtlety of simultaneity" (Cohan, 2023, p. 37).

Those critical disruptive times are unfortunately not confined to a moment in time. With the rise of technology in education, teachers are transitioning into new roles as curators of information, guides for exploration, facilitators of collaboration, mentors for individualized learning (Loble, 2022). They now need to be effective users of digital resources in alignment with their learning objectives and also face the potential disruptions

4.2 Implications for Future Research

One of the main implications of the French teacher's identity is connected with leadership as the French teacher establishes themselves as a leader, an agent of their teaching in their classrooms and at their schools. The teacher-leader plays thus an important role in the constitution and delivery of teaching practices (Hattie, 2023).

Moreover, the image of the French teacher as a leader also provides a statement about the complexity of their identity inside the classroom and outside in the social, cultural, material and technological world (Bennett, 2017). Consequently, the main finding of this research project concerning teacher leadership implies that teacher identity is a central component in French language teaching. The implications are thus far and wide for the French teacher and more widely for L2 teachers. That is what motivates the turn to the wider context of second language teaching to explain further the link between teaching with leadership and teacher identity.

Even though the concept of teacher identity can apply to teaching, one has to concede L2 teacher identity has distinct key features. Hence, throughout this research project and in the literature on the topic, teaching a second language has been viewed as taking place in a social context within the classroom situation and beyond. The language classroom is viewed as a site of transformative practices and social interactions for both students and teachers.

As established before, an L2 classroom is a space of interculturality where the identity of the student and that of the teacher is enacted through multiple ways of acting, thinking, behaving, and negotiating one's persona within the context of the classroom (Gee, 1999). Hence, second language teaching is complex, dynamic, socially constructed, and positively embraced, or not, sometimes. It can also be the site of a reclaimed cultural identity in that it challenges stereotypes. In that case, L2 teacher identity is also political in its endeavour to propose rational and harmonious thinking about prominence in culture in general and cultural diversity and inclusion in particular.

One's identity is indeed seen as constantly being negotiated between the micro, meso and macro levels (Burke & Stets, 2023). French teachers' identities vary from their teacher identity (who they are as a teacher), to the identity they enact in their classroom (meso level), and to their claimed identity as part of a collective entity as second language teachers (macro). The participants claimed identity markers like their scarves or bags for the female teachers or their Coq sportif football t-shirts for the men that distinguish them from the collective of teachers at their schools. They are the French teachers with a distinct identity and are perceived as such. As a further indication of the specificity of second language teacher identity, one could also cite the "aspirational standards" of the AFMLTA (2021) "developed by language teachers for language teachers". These standards provide examples of characteristics that "lead language teachers" should possess as second language teachers in comparison to the general standards sustained by AISTL for all teachers.

Interestingly, when taking a close look at the AFMLTA standards, one comes across first the overarching standards: Educational Theory and Practice, Language and Culture, Language Pedagogy, Ethics and Responsibility, Personal Relationships, Active Engagement with the wider context, and Advocacy. However, the last AFMLTA standard about Personal Characteristics proves to be of utmost importance. It directly sustains the findings and implications of this research project by highlighting that second language teaching depends on the personal characteristics of the L2 teachers.

AFMLTA indeed asserts that the L2 teachers' "personal characteristics" determine and influence their practice and help them reach "aspirational standards" of teaching and being a language teacher. Hence, the research proposes to transform the term "personal characteristics" into that of L2 "teacher identity". The latter term can then be used as a critical tool to rethink ontologically and epistemologically second language teacher education.

As an ontological term, teacher identity is to be understood as the professional identity of teachers formed from the individual and collective understanding of who teachers are and how they view themselves. It exists within the teacher's lifeworld and relates to their sets of beliefs about second language teaching, their enacted role in their classroom and at school, and their projected selves in the school community and beyond (van Putten, 2022). Such a perspective represents teacher identity as an interaction between pedagogy and professional practice born out of the teachers' personal experiences and professional context, at school and beyond.

Epistemologically, it explains how the identity of a teacher is inscribed in the fabric of their personal and collective experience. It is the continual reflexive process that begins with initial teacher education and grows throughout their career as teachers' story who they are and reflect on their practice (Clandinin & Connelly, 1996; Almos, 2022). Subsequently, I would like to propound that not only is teacher identity a concept to contemplate, but it is also a powerful tool. It allows teachers to envisage and design what becomes their philosophy of education or their vision of what motivates their teaching in shallow waters and in deep turbulent times. This is true both at the beginning of their career and during the long years of their teaching career when their initial vision can get blurred by their daily teaching circumstances (Russell & Martin, 2017). It equips L2 teachers with a deep robust confidence that moves them beyond the standards of efficacy imposed by government decisions and policies (Groundwater-Smith & Mockler, 2009) and what is seen as the only solution to the educational challenges of the present times: the need to find and to adhere closely to "what works" (Fahey, 2023).

The research posits that future research on teacher identity is needed. L2 teacher identity has for too long focussed primarily on teachers of English as a second language. It is time to probe into the rich mosaic of the 54 languages that Victoria offers across the education system, to listen to the voices of the teachers of these 54 languages and thus discover teacher identity in a broader sense. There is a vast array of unexplored experiences and uncharted voices that are ready to be heard. As more literature is made available on teacher identity, and on L2 teacher identity, direct and practical links could be applied to improve teaching standards, of which L2 teachers would be the primary agents. Consequently, one can argue that to understand how to teach French, or more broadly, a second language, one needs to understand the lifeworld of teachers, who the teachers are, the professional, political, social, and cultural beings they are and the assigned or claimed identities they bring into their classroom.

Any system's evolution depends on the selection it makes and on the multilayered nodal networks between the individual and the system and the links it creates between those nodes. By choosing to encompass teacher identity as part of teacher education, the evolution of the system involves the evolution of the networks between teachers and the system and the co-evolution of the boundaries of teacher education as it expands to meet the present and the future needs of teachers. This view counteracts overarching discourses about the measurement of teachers' performativity, accountability and standard-based professionalism (Konidari & Samara, 2021). It points out rather that in the crisis situation teaching is in, there is need to listen closely to the voices of teachers as they provide invaluable insight not only for future research but also for policymaking while assuring teachers' and institutional agency and resilience.

5. Concluding Remark

At the conclusion of this project, the participants and I felt a deep implicit and intricate sense of what teaching French means to us and could mean to other French teachers. It has moved us in seamless but profound and sometimes unsettling ways into a sense of wonder about our professional and personal lives. There have been times of excitement, knowing, imagining, storytelling, and silences as our pre-reflective comments cohered to give way to a space where our lived experience is and manifests itself. In this experience, we have reached for blue-sky thinking, entered the unspoken and cultivated a new vocabulary to think at the edge. As this project ends, teaching French, and more widely second languages, calls for knowing, valuing and acting in ways that allow teachers to cultivate a sharp and creative mind and a tactful pedagogy.

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